

FORMATION OF COMPETENCIES IN PRIMARY CLASSES OF BOARDING SCHOOLS FOR CHILDREN WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT

Bannayeva Matluba Olimjon kizi

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami, teacher of the department of "Signal Pedagogy and Inclusive Education"

Khushvaktov Abror Dilshodjon ugli

Tashkent State Pedagogical University named after Nizami
Student of deaf pedagogy and inclusive education 401 group
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Annotation: In boarding schools for hearing-impaired children, their scientific competence is formed from the elementary grades. Competence is the process of applying the acquired knowledge, skills and abilities of the student in his life. Competences are also developed in mathematics lessons. Competencies are developed and technological approaches are used during their education.

Key words: hearing-impaired child, competence, communicative competence, technology, competence of working with information in teaching subjects, competence of self-development.

Introduction:

Mathematics (*in ancient Greek mathema - knowledge, science*) is the science of knowledge based on clear logical observations. Since its original object was counting, it was often referred to as the "science of calculation." In today's mathematics, calculations and even operations on formulas occupy a very small place. Mathematics is the oldest branch of science, with a long history of development, and correspondingly, "What is mathematics?" the answer to the question has also changed and deepened. In Greece, mathematics meant geometry. In the 10th-13th centuries, algebra and trigonometry expanded the concept of mathematics.¹ The science of mathematics was founded by our grandfather Al-Khorazmi. Initially, the term "Al-jabr" was changed to "Algebra". Teaching mathematics to elementary school students with hearing impairments on the basis of pedagogical technologies will help them master the subject more easily. As stated by V.P. Bepalko: Pedagogical technology is the representation - design of the process of student personality formation, which can guarantee pedagogical success, regardless of the teacher's skills.² The subject of pedagogical technology is the design of the educational process and professional training system. A systematic approach covers all the main aspects of the educational system - from defining the goal and designing the educational process, to checking the effectiveness of the new educational system, testing it, and popularizing it. Existing methods and methods of teaching in many cases consist of a set of recommendations for organizing and conducting the educational process, while pedagogical technology is different: firstly, it guarantees the final result, and secondly, it also designs the educational process. According to U.N. Nishonaliyev and B.L. Farberman,

¹ Sanjar Arkabayev (electronic manual) Annotated dictionary of mathematical terms, May 30, 2020, <https://telegra.ph/Matematika-05-30>

² Primary education pedagogy, innovation and integration of 2020 3rd courses for the 2nd semester, <https://fayllar.org/boshlangich-talim-pedagogikasi-innovatsiya-va-integrasiya-fani.html?page=4>

Pedagogical technology is characterized by the clear definition of educational goals, the guarantee of the final result, the reproducibility of the educational process, and the presence of fast feedback. Teaching science based on pedagogical technologies and technological approaches to students with hearing impairments; firstly, it leads to easier learning and understanding in them, and secondly, it arouses interest in science. Various approaches are used in the teaching and education process.

Technology is a Greek word meaning techne-skill, art, logos-concept, teaching.³ The concept of technology is a set of methods and methods used in production processes to obtain a finished product; It is defined as a science that develops and improves such methods and methods. It is the technological approach in the field of education where the study and teaching process are interconnected, their division into groups, the coordination of actions to achieve the intended result in the educational process, sequential, step-by-step implementation, the simultaneous execution of all planned works and actions. implies. Mathematical competences of students with hearing impairment are formed in primary classes based on technological approaches. The main goal of teaching mathematics to hearing impaired children is:

- formation and development of the system of mathematical knowledge and skills necessary for students with hearing impairments to apply their mathematical knowledge in daily activities, study subjects and continue their education;

- formation of students who can successfully operate in a developing society, who can think clearly and clearly, critically, systematically and logically;

- to develop a person who can apply mathematical knowledge and skills to contribute to the modeling and predictive information necessary for society to make independent decisions for its future

- to develop a person who can apply mathematical concepts and strategic approaches to consider and help solve the problems and challenges faced by national and global societies in all disciplines;

- to form a person who can use their mathematical knowledge and understanding of risk to understand and comprehend the information they encounter every day, and thus make rational decisions in all areas of life for the benefit of themselves and others;

- formation of a person who has effective directions of lifelong learning through the ability to understand mathematics and work in the mathematical world; i.e. creativity, curiosity, collaboration, strategic awareness, independence, resilience and resourcefulness.

- it consists in training, creative and critical development of students' creativity focused on designing by connecting their practical activities through observations. Demonstrate skills in thinking and logical analysis, curiosity, problem solving, and innovation.

Along with the formation of mathematical competences of students with hearing impairment in the primary grades, it is determined that they should form basic competences. Competence is the ability to use the theoretical knowledge, practical skills and competencies acquired in science to solve practical and theoretical problems encountered in everyday life.⁴

³ Primary education pedagogy, innovation and integration of 2020 3rd courses for the 2nd semester, <https://fayllar.org/boshlangich-talim-pedagogikasi-innovatsiya-va-integrasiya-fani.html?page=4>

⁴ Core competencies, <https://fayllar.org/tayanch-kompetensiyalar.html>

Competence - (Latin: competences - capable, has the ability) In addition to pure professional knowledge, skills and qualifications, competence also includes initiative, cooperation, ability to work in a group, communicative ability, ability to realistically evaluate, logical thinking, ability to sort and use information. Education aimed at the formation of competences is an education aimed at the formation of competences for practical application of acquired knowledge, skills and qualifications in their personal, professional and social activities. It is appropriate to focus on the formation of basic competences in students with hearing impairments, on the basis of their acquired knowledge and ability to apply them in various situations.

In the formation of communicative competences, it is necessary to teach students to think independently, creatively, fluently express their thoughts in writing and orally, correctly pronounce, explain, and communicate freely. In particular, the science of mathematics has its own scientific language, its own concepts, signs and symbols, and communicating in this language should be considered as a factor in the formation of communicative competences.

It is necessary to regularly use modern information and telecommunication tools that expand the possibilities of effective development of competence in working with information in the teaching of sciences. In this way, students are trained to work with textbooks and various educational resources, to search and analyze information related to mathematics from various sources, and to form the skills of working with information media in compliance with information security, using various practical software packages and supplies, mobile devices (phones, tablets and other gadgets).) is recommended.

To have qualities based on universal human values in the formation of self-development competence, to love the Motherland, to have knowledge about society and nature, to strive for innovations and to make independent decisions based on acquired theoretical knowledge, to be aware of and involved in progressive and innovative changes taking place in society, always it is necessary to strive to acquire modern knowledge and skills, and to teach them how to use them in everyday life. Here, through thorough study of mathematics, students learn discipline, look at every problem as a mathematical problem, and become persistent in solving it.

Formation of socio-emotional and civic competence consists in acquiring knowledge about civic duty, social and political development, emergency situations, environmental problems, and developing organizational skills in understanding artistic and artistic works and preserving them. Also, mathematics educates them in the spirit of honesty, indifference to injustice and loyalty to the motherland. By carefully teaching mathematics, the ground is created to develop students as active citizens of society.

The standards should cover all students as widely as possible from the initial period of education, and create appropriate conditions to ensure the opportunity for their full participation in the learning process and the maximum level of participation of students with special needs in the field of education. The standards set clear milestones that all students must meet to prepare for further education and employment. More specifically, standards define what students understand and can do. These competencies define what students with special needs should understand and be able to do through learning mathematics. One of the hallmarks of understanding in mathematics is the student's ability to justify whether a

particular mathematical expression is true or false, or where a particular mathematical rule comes from, based on the student's level of mathematical mastery. Equally important is the understanding of mathematical concepts and the ability to perform typical operations, which are assessed using standard tasks of a certain level of complexity.

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